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Pesticide residues in spices and herbs: Sample preparation methods and determination by chromatographic techniques

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ABSTRACT

Most widely developed approaches for pesticide residues analysis in spices and herbs present serious limitations; this is because of the high number of interferences that they typically contain, which makes it difficult to identify/quantify compounds in a considerable percentage of cases. Different strategies are applied to overcome these difficulties including extensive clean-up steps, dilution of the extracts, more selective detection techniques and other effective methods. However, there is a strong matrix effect present with the most complex matrices. Recent advances with new clean-up sorbents and the greater sensitivity and selectivity provided by modern mass spectrometers facilitates the determination of pesticide residues in these complex matrices at the desired limits of quantification. This review summarizes the main sample extraction and clean-up procedures for pesticide residues in spices and herbs published between 2008 and 2018, evaluating both their strengths and limitations. In addition, the high-end mass spectrometry detection methods are critically discussed.

Keywords: Spices Herbs; Sample preparation; Pesticide residue analysis; Chromatography; Mass spectrometry

Abbreviations

DAD	Diode array detector
d-SPE	Dispersive solid-phase extraction
ECD	Electron capture detector
ESI	Electrospray ion source
FID	Flame ionization detector
FPD	Flame photometric detector
GC-HR-TOF-MS	Gas chromatography high-resolution time- of-flight mass spectrometry
GC-QqQ-MS/MS	Gas chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometry
GPC	Gel permeation chromatography
HRAM	High-resolution accurate mass spectrometry
LC-QqQ-MS/MS	Liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometry
LOQ	Quantitation limit
ME	Matrix effect
MRLs	Maximum residue limits
MRM	Multiple reaction monitoring
MSPD	Matrix solid-phase dispersion
NPD	Nitrogen phosphorous detector
PSA	Primary secondary amine
SIM	Selected ion monitoring
SPE	Solid-phase extraction

1. Introduction

Spices and herbs are important vegetable products used in relatively small quantities to provide pleasing flavor, aroma and/or color characteristics in foods (pepper, capsicums, nutmeg, cardamom, oregano, thyme, coriander and saffron, etc). Spices comprise the aromatic seeds, roots, buds, bark, rhizomes, pods, flowers (or parts thereof), berries or other fruits from a variety of plants. Herbs are leafy spices, some of which, such as coriander and dill, can be considered both spice seeds and leafy herbs [1,2]. Several spices and herbs have been used extensively for medicinal (peppermint, thyme, basil, bay leaf, clove, rosemary, ginger, fennel, etc) and preservative or insecticidal purposes (allspice, chives, clove, cumin, fennel, etc). It has been demonstrated that many spices and herbs possess antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, anti-rheumatic, lipid-lowering, hepatoprotective, nephroprotective, antimutagenic and anticancer properties, as well as their gastro-protective and antiulcer activities [3,4].

One of the current major issues regarding spices in terms of food safety and trade is the presence of microbiological agents and pesticide residues. The development of effective analytical procedures for the determination of pesticides in these types of matrices remains a problem of considerable importance. The presence of high concentrations of numerous natural molecules and redox-active secondary metabolites or antioxidants (ascorbic acid, carotenoids, flavonoids, polyphenols, glutathione, tocopherols, tocotrienols and enzymes) and also apolar molecules of essential oils such as monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes, may hinder extraction and analysis due to low pesticide recoveries and the presence of interferences or ion suppression. Consequently, sample preparation, especially the clean-up step, has become a key issue in spice and herb analysis.

As current clean-up methods are not able to remove the complex co-extractives that make it difficult to identify/quantify some of the analytes of interest, highly selective techniques are employed for routine analysis in food control laboratories such as gas and liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometry (GC-QqQ-MS/MS and LC-QqQ-MS/MS). Co-eluting compounds generate two main effects: 1) isobaric interferences in multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) transitions, and therefore false negative detection as the ion ratio can differ from the standard, and 2) signal suppression or enhancement, commonly called the "matrix effect", which can detrimentally affect accuracy, sensitivity and reproducibility as well as system maintenance [5]. Therefore,

further efforts in applying corrective methods or exhaustive clean-up procedures are necessary to reduce matrix effects when analyzing spice and herb samples. Recently, twenty- five different blank matrices, including two herbs (parsley and celery), extracted with the four most common extraction methods used in routine analysis (citrate QuEChERS with/without PSA clean- up, ethyl acetate and the Dutch mini-Luke “NL” methods) were evaluated by both GC-QqQ-MS/MS and LC-QqQ-MS/MS. The results showed that parsley was one of the matrices with the highest percentage of observed interferences, meaning that none of the tested extraction methods achieved effective extraction for the totality of the pesticides analyzed [6].

In this work, the emphasis is on a brief evaluation of the advantages and limitations of the developed methods. The strategies currently used to eliminate or reduce matrix effects are also highlighted. Furthermore, traditional and advanced detection techniques based on mass spectrometry are critically reviewed in this article.

2. Regulation and monitoring data

The presence of pesticide residues in foods, including spices and herbs is an important concern to human health, leading several government authorities and international organizations such as EPA [7] and Codex Alimentarius [8] to establish tolerances or maximum residue levels (MRLs) to regulate pesticide levels. In Europe, the occurrence of residues in different products, including spices and herbs, is controlled according to European Union (EU) Regulation N^o 396/2005 and Regulation 149/2008 [9,10], sub- dividing spices into sub-groups based on the parts of plants from which they are obtained and setting the MRLs for some spices in each sub-group rather than for all spices. MRLs range from 0.01 to 400 mg/kg. These data are regularly updated in the EU Pesticide Database (<http://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/eu-pesticides-database/>). However, MRLs in the EU are only established for fresh commodities, not for primary processed or dried products where typically, enrichment of the pesticide residues takes place. Therefore, the concentration resulting from the drying process should be taken into account when determining the MRL. The European Spice Association (ESA) recommends the application of dehydration factors for dried products in order to have harmonized MRL assessment [11]. The resulting values are calculated with the following formula:

$$\text{Dehydration factor} = 1/[1 - (\%H_2O/100)]$$

On the other hand, the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) offers a compilation of processing factors on its website (<http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/349/bfr-compilation-of-processing-factors.xlsx>) which contains more than 6500 processing factors for a total of 800 differently named matrices.

Despite the possibility of assuming that the pesticides used on spices are comparable to those used on similar crops in the same area, there is little monitoring data on this commodity type. For example, up until now spices have not been included in EU-coordinated monitoring programs [12,13] so, data on the most frequently found pesticides and the percentages of samples with residues above the MRL remain relatively scarce. In general, spices have received little attention because the doses consumed have been considered very small. Among the different pesticide groups, the presence of organochlorine pesticide in spices was commonly reported in monitoring studies performed from 1999 to 2010 in China [14-16], Brazil [17] and Egypt [18]. More recently, the available monitoring data [19,20] indicated a higher probability of occurrence for bifenthrin, DDT, cypermethrin, chlorpyrifos, triazophos, carbendazim, dimethoate, endosulfan, ethion, tefluthrin, profenofos, metalaxyl, propamocarb, and trifluralin. Some of these, like DDT and triazophos, are banned in the European market. Carbendazim, cypermethrin, dimethoate, endosulfan and ethion have been frequently reported in The European Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) or found at levels above the MRL. Pesticide residues in these matrices have been mentioned in the literature, sometimes in concentrations exceeding the MRLs. Ferrer Amate et al. [5] studied the incidence and range of pesticides in several spice samples (paprika, curry, black and white pepper, chilli, curcuma, nutmeg and ginger) purchased from supermarkets throughout Austria as well as from local retail markets or bazaars; the country of origin for most of them being Turkey and China. Carbendazim and carbaryl were found in several paprika samples at levels above the MRL (25-386 µg/kg and 7-501 µg/kg for carbendazim and carbaryl, respectively). Other compounds like dimethoate, carbofuran, imidacloprid, methomyl, spinosad and methamidophos were also determined in paprika, curry, black and white pepper, chilli and curcuma. Maggi et al. [21] investigated the presence of pesticide residues and other contaminants in saffron. a-HCH, simazine, propazine, diazinon and sulprofos were found at levels higher than the fixed MRL while alachlor, atrazine, ametryn, chlorpyrifos and, molinate were detected at concentrations lower than

the MRLs.

[Table 1](#) shows MRL exceedances from monitoring programs carried out in the EU in 2016 on pesticide residues in peppercorn (black, green and white), which were recently published by the European Food Safety Authority (The 2016 European Union report on pesticide residues in food, EFSA 2018). Only those results without an asterisk were non-compliant, considering a 50% expanded measurement uncertainty. In the framework of reinforced import controls, some targeted sampling at border controls, according to Regulation 669/2009, were included based on previously observed high incidences of non-compliant spices imported from certain countries and/or notifications under the Rapid Alert System of the European Commission. In 2016, Chinese celery, basil, mint, coriander and parsley from third countries were monitored by this border control. Only two samples out of 12 of fresh or chilled herbs from Vietnam were non-compliant.

3. Extraction procedures

Different extraction procedures have been developed for the determination of pesticides in spices and herbs. One of the most demanding tasks for routine pesticide analysis in foodstuffs is to use multi-residue and multi-matrix analytical methods with a large analytical scope. In general, work on complex spice and herb matrices only afford a low scope of analysis and method performance can vary even within the same type of spice or herb, making the definition of representative matrices with similar analytical behavior difficult.

For dry samples, a key aspect in achieving reliable recovery studies is the spiking process. Dry spices are aged matrices that have their pores closed, which hinders the penetration of pesticides into their tissues during the fortification process. Thus, they must be fortified with the mix by thoroughly soaking the entire sample and then stirring it to ensure an effective homogenization procedure; afterwards, they have to be dried. However, little information has been published on this aspect. On the other hand, prior to extraction, for dry spices it is necessary to swell the sample with water for 1 h to hydrate it and to allow the extraction solvent to penetrate thus obtaining better extraction efficiency [22].

[Table 2](#) and [Table 3](#) summarize the methods reported over the last 10 years (2008-2018) according to the detection system, and also outline the most representative extraction procedures to determine pesticide residues in spice and herb samples.

3.1. Classical extraction and clean up procedures

Only a few works using classical methods such as liquid-solid extraction (LSE) have been published for the analysis of pesticide residues in spices and herbs (Table 2). Methods based on LSE require large volumes of organic solvents (>50 mL), they are also time-consuming and difficult to automate. It has been found that a decrease in solvent polarity (acetonitrile → n-hexane) led to reduced solubility of polar co-extracts facilitating the analysis, but poor recoveries were obtained for polar or semi-polar pesticides ($\log K_{ow} < 4$) [23]. An increase in the amount of extraction solvent volume and time can result in improved pesticide recoveries. Generally, the extract needs an additional clean-up step (GPC or SPE) before chromatographic analysis [23,24]. The combination of shaking (30 s - 1 min) and ultrasonication (10-30 min) has been used in LSE to enhance extraction efficiency from spice matrices [5].

GPC is a highly effective and robust methodology used for the clean-up of extracts containing a broad range of co-extracted compounds and it is based on the great difference in molecular weight between the co-extracted molecular interferences (e.g. flavonoids, pigments, proteins, polysaccharides and alkaloids) and the target pesticides, which are smaller molecules that penetrate the small pores in the stationary phase particles while the large interference molecules do not. An advantage of GPC is that it decreases the maintenance of the analytical instrument under working conditions and extends the lifetime of the columns since the co-extractives are eluted first. Although this clean-up method is amenable to automation, it has disadvantages such as the high consumption of hazardous organic solvents (e.g., n-hexane, ethyl acetate and cyclohexane), and the lengthy extraction time, which does not fit well into routine analysis workflows. An SPE step using a tandem primary/secondary amine modified silica (PSA)/graphitized carbon black (GCB) bed cartridge following the GPC of dried ground ginseng root ethyl acetate extracts has been used for further clean-up of co-extractives [25]. The combination of GPC and SPE offered sufficient clean-up whereas GPC or SPE alone presented significant interferences in qualitative and quantitative analysis of 170 organohalogen and organophosphorus pesticides, isomers and metabolites by GC-MS and GC-HR-TOF-MS.

SPE is generally applied to the clean-up extracts of various extraction solvents (Table 2). It is a good alternative to the time consuming GPC technique which

requires substantial amounts of expensive high purity and environmentally hazardous solvents. Examples of published studies and procedures include: a study of conditions for clean-up with silica gel packed in a Pasteur glass pipette to determine organochlorine and pyrethroid pesticides in white and black pepper by GC-ECD [26]; the optimization of SPE clean-up for pesticide monitoring in commercial herbal medicines by GC-MS/MS, based on the type of SPE sorbent (C₁₈, Carb/NH₂), and the type and volume of the eluting solution [27]. These methods showed good recovery and precision results. LOQs were in the 2-200 µg/kg (GC-ECD) and 0.03-12 µg/kg (GC-MS/MS) ranges. Very recently, the introduction of an SPE-based clean-up step using hydrophilic-lipophilic-balance (HLB) cartridges proved advantageous in minimizing the false negatives for non-target multiresidue analysis of 199 pesticides using ultra-HPLC-quadrupole-Orbitrap mass spectrometry in spice matrices, including black pepper, cardamom, chili, coriander, cumin, and turmeric. The limit of quantification was mostly at 10 µg/kg, except for black pepper and turmeric with an LOQ at 20 µg/kg; recoveries were between 70 and 120% and RSDs <20% [28].

Matrix solid-phase dispersion (MSPD) is an extraction method based on the use of the same solid supports as in SPE, which are used as grinding material for sample disruption. The sample/solid support mixture is crushed with a mortar and pestle. After this homogenization step, the blend is transferred with a spatula to an SPE column. MSPD can be considered a good alternative to liquid-liquid extraction. It consumes less solvent, generates little waste, saves time, and the occurrence of troublesome emulsions are avoided. However, MSPD is a manual procedure affecting good reproducibility, so it is not easy to operate in routine analysis. Various methods have been proposed for the determination of pesticide residues in different herbs using classical sorbent materials such as octadecylsilyl (C₁₈), Florisil and silica gel [23,29]. Łozowicka et al. [23] optimized the process of preparation, extraction and purification of herbal samples using MSPD and liquid-solid extraction (LSE) for the determination of a wide range of pesticides (approximately 163) by GC-NPD/ECD. For MSPD, the optimum extraction conditions were obtained with activated Florisil but experiments showed that the final MSPD extract contained a large amount of interfering peaks with retention times close to those of the target pesticides. To reduce the level of the co-extracted matrix, the addition of octadecyl (C₁₈) as a clean-up sorbent at the bottom of the chromatography column was necessary. Comparing MSPD and LSE procedures, MSPD provides time savings (extraction up to 15 min), less consumption of toxic

solvents and it is simpler to perform than LSE. MSPD successfully recovered 155 multi-class pesticides (R>70%), whereas LSE was effective with only 142 pesticides. Otherwise, the MSPD extraction technique offered better results in terms of the amount of isolated matrix co-extracts with LOQs ranging from 5 to 40 µg/kg. Data on the matrix effect were not discussed.

A promising alternative to liquid-solid solvent extraction is supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) with carbon dioxide (CO₂). CO₂ has the advantages of a low critical point (T_c = 304.13 K, P_c = 73.773 bar) thus preserving thermo-labile pesticides, low toxicity, and minimal safety concerns regarding environmental and hardware damage. A way to increase the solvating power of CO₂ is to add an organic co-solvent into the SFE system as a modifier. Alternatively, SFE using pressurized CO₂ overcomes the drawback of requiring organic solvents but incurs high operating and instrumentation costs. Machalova et al. [30] optimized the extraction of botanical pesticides from *Pelargonium graveolens* using SFE to improve the extraction yields, selectivity and pesticidal activity of the CO₂ extracts, compared to isolates obtained by maceration in different solvents and hydrodistillation. However, in the 20 years since its appearance this technique has not been consolidated in routine analysis.

Another technique is pressurized liquid extraction (PLE), which is a greener technology compared to conventional extraction techniques (Soxhlet and LSE) because it provides advantages such as lower solvent volumes, an automatic procedure for the simultaneous extraction of multiple samples, and a significant reduction in the extraction time. The major drawbacks of PLE include the requirement for additional sample clean-up and the high instrumentation costs, which result in scarce popular usage. A selective PLE and GC-MS/MS method was developed by Du et al. [31] for the simultaneous determination of 52 pesticide residues in four herbs including the root of *Pueraria thomsonii* Benth., *Pogostemon cablin* Benth., *Houttuynia cordata* Thunb. and *Disoscorea opposita* Thunb. The developed extraction method integrated extraction and clean-up processes into one step. The results obtained, based on GC-MS/MS and including 17 retention time windows, each comprising between one and seven MRM transitions, showed that interfering substances (11-12 and 19-20 min) compromised the chromatographic separation; however, the extracted ion chromatograms were able to overcome the problem of poor separation. Good recoveries between 81 and 118% with low RSDs (3-12%) were obtained. The LOQs achieved were high (1000-10000 µg/kg) so they were not effective for control purposes.

3.2. Miniaturized techniques

The need to eliminate or reduce solvent volumes, and the overall sample preparation time for the extraction of organic residues from food samples, has led to the development of several new extraction approaches. When applying extraction on a smaller scale, sample homogeneity is important. Some spices are hard and so it is not easy to homogenize them into a fine powder.

Different miniaturized techniques, including stir bar sorptive extraction and solvent microextraction, have been applied to the analysis of spices and herbs. Stir bar sorptive extraction (SBSE) is based on sorptive extraction, whereby the analytes are extracted into a polymer coating such as polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) on a magnetic stirring rod. The main limitation of this technique is the commercially available PDMS extractant phase, which is a non-polar polymer, thus the polar compounds are poorly extracted. A sensitive SBSE method for the determination of 46 organic contaminants by GC-MS in saffron was developed by Maggi et al. [21]. Detection limits were lower than 1 µg/kg for the tested compounds, except for simazine. The reproducibility was noteworthy and indicated the robustness of this method with RSDs around 15% at 10 µg/kg.

An interesting alternative for sample preparation is liquid-phase microextraction (LPME) because of its simplicity, effectiveness, low cost, minimum solvent use and excellent sample clean-up capability. Different configurations of this technique have emerged (static/dynamic LPME, single drop, and hollow-fiber-based liquid-phase microextraction). However, these methods suffer from the serious drawbacks of a poorly reproducible extractant phase and long extraction times. In 2006, Rezaee et al. introduced a new and promising liquid-phase microextraction technique termed dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME) [32]. It is based on a ternary component solvent system, in which extraction and disperser solvents are rapidly introduced into the sample to form a cloudy solution. Extraction equilibrium is quickly achieved due to the extensive contact surface between the extraction solvent droplets and the sample. The advantages of the DLLME method are simplicity of operation, rapidity, low cost, high recovery, a high enrichment factor and environmental benignity. There are many examples of pesticide-targeted DLLME methods now being used in environmental water, and biological and pharmacological analysis, but these methods only cover a smaller number of pesticides. Efforts have been made by a few authors trying to develop

methods for food samples, mainly fruits and vegetables, which ended up with non-specific chemical targets and limited analyte numbers. With complex herb matrices, limitations still exist due to high glycoside and flavonoid contents [33]. This fact has contributed to a common restriction on the capacity of partition-based extraction methods. A simple and sensitive DLLME method was developed, dedicated specifically to determining ten organophosphorus pesticides using GC-MS in different dried herbs [34]. The novelty of this procedure lies in the use of an organic disperser as the solid sample leachant to further improve organophosphorus extractability. The method was fully validated for robust clean-up and preconcentration in five dried herbs. It features minimal sample and solvent consumption (0.1 g and 1.3 mL, respectively), a short analysis time (9 min), superior enrichment factors (from 51 to 99) and ultra-sensitive quantification limits in the sub-ppt range.

3.3. Extraction procedures based on the QuEChERS method

Nowadays, QuEChERS is the most frequently used sample treatment procedure in the analysis of pesticide residues in food. This method [35], involves liquid-solid extraction using acetonitrile and extract clean-up using d-SPE. The most important advantages of QuEChERS include very accurate results, high sample throughput, low solvent consumption and waste generation, being relatively inexpensive, easy to automate and having a wide scope of application. The QuEChERS approach has also proved capable of being modified to new challenges with a wide variety of analytes and commodities. Although modified QuEChERS was shown to be efficient for hundreds of pesticides in several kinds of food matrices [36], using dispersive solid-phase extraction, as the clean-up in QuEChERS, is not effective at removing the complex co-extractives from spice and herb matrices that may hinder analyte identification and confirmation. Therefore, the introduction of any new extraction/clean-up modification to effectively minimize the matrix effect, while maintaining satisfactory recoveries, helps to address the needs of pesticide residue laboratories. The reported adaptations or modifications for pesticide residue analysis in spices and herbs are discussed below:

With respect to the introduction of buffering salts, EU [37] and AOAC [38] versions of the buffered QuEChERS extraction method were used to obtain organic pesticide extracts for spice and herb analysis [22,39-41]. Buffers were introduced to ensure a constant pH value during the extraction of different matrices in order to minimize degradation of base and acid labile pesticides and to

provide recoveries higher than 70% for some pH-dependent pesticides such as thiabendazole, pymetrozine and imazalil. Comparative studies have shown that the EU version provides weaker ionic strength conditions leading to cleaner extracts than the AOAC version, and ensures higher recoveries for most acidic compounds (>70%) [22,42]. In fact, the EU version utilizing d-SPE with PSA sorbent for matrix clean-up was considered the best choice. Certain matrices, such as black pepper, have a high pH value (7.8) during the soaking period, which causes low recoveries of base-sensitive pesticides such as clofentezine, dichlofluanid, naled, thiodicarb, thiophanate-methyl and tolylfluanid. The addition of 0.5-2% (v/v) formic acid (FA) to the sample prior to extraction significantly improves the recoveries of polar, acidic pesticides (i.e., clopyralid and dicamba) from high pH matrices, without compromising the recoveries of basic analytes (except pymetrozine). Moreover, the low pH of the extract minimizes the losses of base-sensitive pesticides. Several authors have observed low recovery of base-sensitive compounds from dry matrices when FA was added into the extraction mixture after the soaking period. Consequently, FA addition before soaking is recommended to obtain recovery of these compounds within an acceptable range (70-120%) [22].

Concerning the extraction solvent, acetonitrile (AcN) is the most frequently applied in multiresidue methods, not only for spice and herb analysis but also for many other matrices [36]. It has been reported that ethyl acetate has a lower extraction efficiency (recoveries < 60%) than that of AcN in cardamom matrix [39]. AcN enables extraction of more polar analytes with relatively small amounts of non-polar co-extractives but there is also a higher percentage of polar interferences present at high concentration levels in these types of matrices. Exchanging the solvent for ethyl acetate in the final AcN extract proved efficient in reducing some early-eluting matrix co-extractives and improving sensitivity in the determination of 243 pesticide residues in cardamom by gas chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (GC-MS/MS) [39]. The solvent exchange helped to reduce the matrix co-extract by up to 60% and reduced the matrix effects of triflurosulfuron, tebutiuron, disulfoton, terbufos and lindane.

Regarding the sample mass, a lower amount is recommended for these complex matrices in order to obtain fewer interferences in the total ion chromatograms (TICs). This may affect the sensitivity, recovery and precision of the analysis. The best results have been obtained using a 2 g sample mass [26,39,40,43,44] obtaining total sample injection of 1 g of matrix in 1 mL of extract. RSDs $\geq 20\%$ and recoveries above 130% have been reported for higher sample masses (3-5 g).

Conversely, more pesticides had recoveries below 40% when a 1 g sample mass was used compared to a 5 g mass [39,43]. In many cases, PSA-, C18- and GCB-based sorbents were used for cleaning spice and herb samples during the d-SPE step in the QuEChERS technique, which coextract amounts of matrix with the target analytes. However, these sorbents can not remove a large percentage of co-extractives, which remain in the final sample extract and can also exhibit nonselective interactions with analytes. The applications and limitations of the most commonly used d-SPE sorbents are summarized in Table 4.

An alternative to d-SPE sorbents is to use zirconium dioxide nanoparticles, which have a high surface area per m² (surface area >100 m²/g); however, they also result in more analyte loss [45,46] (see Table 4). Pesticide determination in spices and herbs using these kinds of sorbents has hardly been explored. Results for dried herb matrices indicated that the matrix effects were not sufficiently reduced (over 20% of pesticides were above 50% ME) and recoveries <60% were only obtained for about 25% of the analytes [43].

Two other sorbents that are rarely used for the clean-up of herb and spice samples are ChloroFiltr and ENVI-Carb. A comparative study of these d-SPE sorbents for the determination of 235 pesticides in dried herbs was carried out by Rutkowska et al. [43]. ChloroFiltr is a polymeric-based sorbent recommended especially for herbs, which can reduce the amount of chlorophyll with no loss in the recovery of structurally planar analytes. ENVI-Carb is a graphitized carbon sorbent used to remove pigments, polyphenols and other polar compounds. The combination of ChloroFiltr/PSA/ MgSO₄ provided a wider spectrum of pigment adsorption but, unfortunately, over 20% of the pesticides (out of 235) had unacceptable recoveries and showed MEs above 50%. Better results were achieved using a PSA/ENVI-Carb/MgSO₄ combination, with recovery values in the 60-130% range for most pesticides and consistent results (≤20% RSD), in which 65-72% exhibited soft MEs (<±20%) [43].

A new material applied to complex matrices is EMR-Lipid. This material has proven to be efficient for multi-residue pesticide analysis in fatty matrices [47,48]. Urban et al. [49] compared various d-SPE sorbents of the QuEChERS extraction method (PSA, C18 and Z-Sep) and EMR-Lipid for the determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in food of plant origin, including curry spice powder. The MgSO₄/PSA/C18 clean-up was preferred due to slightly higher analyte recovery, the lesser price and the availability of ready-to-use kits. Hakme et al. [50] applied QuEChERS citrate for the analysis of 205 pesticides in cayenne and black pepper, which are representative of complex dried spices. QuEChERS citrate using

EMR-Lipid sorbent resulted in the cleanest extract out of Z-sep, PSA, Oasis® Prime HLB, and Supelclean™ Ultra cartridges.

Freezing-out prior to d-SPE has been employed in the analysis of 235 pesticides in dried herb matrices for better removal of fatty or high-protein coextracted matrix compounds [43]. With respect to adding the freezing-out step, some studies stated no real benefits since some coextracted matrix compounds may still be coextracted, so further clean-up is still desirable; in addition, including a freezing-out step increases manual labor when applying the QuEChERS protocol, thus making this procedure lengthier [51].

Table 3 summarize the relevant QuEChERS applications used in the analysis of pesticides in spices and herbs. In general, the QuEChERS method provided mean recoveries between 70 and 120%, with few exceptions, as well as relative standard deviations (RSDs) typically below 20%; nonetheless, medium or strong matrix effects were shown in most of the published methods. In GC applications, signal enhancement phenomena were typically observed when compared with solvent, which is in accordance with compound behavior in GC systems [6]. In contrast with LC applications, the ion suppression of the analytes caused by the presence of ionic species, polar compounds and organic molecules, was obtained for the most part. The LOQs ranged from 1 to 250 µg/kg; thus these LOQ values were, in certain cases, higher than the MRLs (250 µg/kg for butachlor, chlozolinate, dichlofluanid, endrin, pentachloroanisole, prochloraz and propargite).

4. Sample dilution

Diluting the sample extract is a simple and commonly used alternative that most protocols apply to overcome the matrix effect in multiresidue pesticide methods for complex matrices; however, this option can affect the method's detection capability because, at the same time, it implies a reduction in the concentration of the analytes. It is noticeable that, where ESI is applied as the ion source, increased signal by dilution can be observed because of the decrease in the matrix suppression effects. Therefore, the implementation of a dilution approach to diminish matrix effects depends on the sensitivity of the analytical instrumentation (GC-QqQ-MS/MS, LC-QqQ-MS/MS, GC-HR-MS/MS or LC-HR-MS/MS) and the recoveries of the pesticides with the analytical method still needing to meet the required detection limit for pesticide analysis in spice samples. A contribution by Amate et al. [5] provided an approach which involves a 20-times dilution factor

without any further clean-up step; this proved to be enough to reduce the matrix effects and opens up the possibility of performing quantification that complies with the EU legal requirements; however, a significant matrix effect was still observed in black pepper, where 67% of the studied compounds showed strong signal suppression.

In the case of high-resolution MS, where sensitivity is lower than in QqQ-MS/MS, the published methods avoid sample dilution focusing on different clean-up procedures in order to reduce the matrix co-extractives and decrease false identifications. A novel screening method was reported by Goon et al. [28] for non-target multiresidue analysis of pesticides using ultra-HPLC-quadrupole-Orbitrap mass spectrometry in spice matrices. Samples were extracted using the QuEChERS method and the inclusion of an SPE clean-up step with hydrophilic-lipophilic-balance (HLB) cartridges, which improved the efficiency of the HRAM analysis. Reinholds et al. [40] applied a freezing-out extraction method for the analysis of mycotoxins and pesticide residues in spices using ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) coupled to high-resolution Orbitrap mass spectrometry. The efficiency and detection sensitivity were compared to the results obtained using a UHPLC-QqQ-MS/MS.

5. Analytical instrumentation for pesticides in herbs and spices

The earliest analytical methods reported for pesticide determination in spice and herb analysis using gas chromatography (GC) employed a variety of detectors such as ECD [24], NPD [23,52], FID [30] and FPD [53]. However, these detection methods demonstrated limited and inaccurate identification/quantitation due to the interferences that co-elute at the same retention time as the studied pesticides. The LOQs achieved were between 1 and 200 µg/kg. In the difficult case of pepper, a study developed for the determination of organochlorine and pyrethroid pesticides using LSE and SPE with silica gel followed by analysis using GC-ECD showed LOQs at 20 µg/kg for most pesticides, except for permethrin which was at 100 µg/kg [26].

Despite the low selectivity of LC-DAD detection, an approach to determine seven pesticides in herb extracts using SPE coupled with two-dimensional planar chromatography in combination with HPLC-DAD has been reported [54]. This procedure is inexpensive but the LOQ levels achieved were high (250-3375 µg/kg); therefore, this does not comply with EU regulations. Such shortcomings were

improved upon using mass spectrometry detectors (GC-MS and LC-MS) because of the greater sensitivity and selectivity they provide. They have been the gold standard for determining pesticide residues for the last 20 years [34,55-60]. Good LOQs, between 1.5 and 50 µg/kg, were achieved from the analysis of 195 pesticides in herbs using GC-MS with analyte protectants [58]. Another study developed to determine of 234 pesticides in herbs using d-SPE sample preparation and GC-MS determination showed LOQs below 50 µg/kg for most compounds [61]. With the improvements in MS systems, several types of mass spectrometers are now available. Triple quadrupole MS offers benefits such as increased selectivity and sensitivity, lower LOQs, improved S/N, wider linear range, and improved accuracy. Moreover, it can be used for monitoring a larger number of pesticides in a short run time. Despite the dominance of GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS methods in multiresidue pesticide analysis, these useful tools are not as selective for certain complex matrices. Since they work at the unit resolution level, the identification capabilities of quadrupole mass analyzers are limited when the extraction solvent contains isobaric compounds. Trace analysis may be compromised severely by these interferences causing inaccurate quantitation, retention time shifts, decreased sensitivity and ruggedness, and even false positive/negative results. The presence of common transitions between the matrix and pesticide affects the ion ratio, making the difference 30% higher than that expected, as established in the Analytical Quality Control (AQC) procedures [62]. Multiresidue analyses carried out using tandem mass spectrometry instruments have been reported in the determination of 74 and 116 pesticides in herbs [63,64]. The combination of modified QuEChERS and GC-MS/MS offered excellent accuracy and sensitivity, LOQs were less than 10 µg/kg for most pesticides and, at the LOQs and ten times the LOQs, the mean recoveries of almost all pesticides were within 70-120%, with RSDs lower than 20%. However, medium or high matrix effects appeared in many pesticides.

High-resolution MS is a promising approach with important advantages related to a more conclusive identification due to the mass accuracy obtained, and the retrospective analysis. However, current mass platforms have sensitivities 5-times lower than with QqQ-MS/MS, making it difficult to achieve LOQs in line with the MRLs. A comparison of GC-MS with GC-HR-TOFMS for the determination of 170 organohalogenated and organophosphorus pesticides in ginseng root showed that the HR-TOFMS sensitivity was equivalent to a quadrupole operated in SIM mode, with average LOQs in the low µg/kg range. For several pesticides, the sensitivity of

HR-TOFMS was better than that obtained by qMS, while less sensitivity resulted for a few pesticides. HR-TOFMS provided added accurate mass information on the studied pesticides to aid identification; this was not present when only using a qMS SIM acquisition [25]. Studies have been published for the multiresidue analysis of pesticides in spices using ultra-high performance- HPLC-Orbitrap mass spectrometry following QuEChERS extraction. Six spice matrices, including black pepper, cardamom, chili, coriander, cumin, and turmeric were studied using sequential full-scan (resolution = 70,000), and variable data independent acquisition (vDIA) with nine consecutive fragmentation events (resolution = 17,500) [28]. The LOQs of 199 pesticides were mostly at 10 µg/kg, except for black pepper and turmeric with LOQs at 20 µg/kg which was adequate for EU-MRLs compliances; recoveries were within 70-120% and RSDs <20%. The quantitative performance of this Orbitrap-MS method had agreements in residue values between 78 and 100% compared to LC-MS/MS. A further study developed for the determination of 134 pesticides and 11 mycotoxins in paprika showed good agreement with the results obtained using QqQ-MS/MS. However, the higher resolving power of Orbitrap-MS provided an important benefit by diminishing the signals of interfering compounds from the paprika samples [40].

Apart from sample preparation and dilution, other methods for avoiding or reducing matrix effects to allow correct quantitation include calibration strategies such as: (a) the matrix-matched standard [5,62], (b) the internal standard method [61,62] and (c) the standard addition method [62] or alternatively (d) changing the chromatographic or (e) mass spectrometric conditions. One of the most commonly used methods for avoiding the matrix effect during calibration are the matrix-matched calibration standards (a), where a representative matrix should be used to prepare the calibration solutions. However, the matrix effect varies from commodity to commodity, and the matrix-matched calibration of one spice commodity does not correct the ion suppression/enhancement of the MS signal for another spice commodity, even from the same type of spice. For example, Fig. 1 shows the different matrix effects in the quantitation of aldicarb, amitraz, carbaryl, epoxiconazole, imazalil, indoxacarb and triadimefon on various spice matrices, using the signal obtained with the same pesticide concentrations in solvent solution as the reference. Consequently, it is necessary to implement matrix-matched solutions for each type of commodity. This requirement becomes a disadvantage for laboratories analyzing a larger number of different sample types. Another effective approach to compensate for the matrix effect is applying the internal

standard method (b); nevertheless, the high cost of isotope-labeled compounds and their poor availability are limitations for MRMs. Although the standard addition method (c) is tedious given the large number of samples that must be analyzed, it is a good solution for avoiding matrix effects. Other methods described in the literature include lengthening the run times by changing the chromatographic conditions (d) to avoid coelution of analytes and interfering compounds [65-67] or finding selective ion transitions by changing the mass spectrometric conditions (e) to reduce the occurrence of matrix effects in the ion source [68]. However, these approaches can be time-consuming [69].

6. Conclusions

Nowadays, the analysis of pesticide residues in spices and herbs represents a difficult challenge for laboratories, because it typically involves a very high number of co-extractives, which can lead to errors in identification and quantitation. The QuEChERS method is the most frequently used pretreatment procedure in routine pesticide residue analysis for these commodities, generally providing acceptable results. However, its suitability has not been fully demonstrated for extremely difficult cases such as black pepper or cayenne at low concentration such as 0.01 mg/kg. New sorbents for the d-SPE or SPE step, which are more efficient at removing the interferences involved in these matrices without affecting analyte recovery, are expected in the future, opening up a promising research line is the use of dual sorbents.

Using a high dilution factor (≥ 10) obtaining total sample injection in the extract of around 0.1 g has been widely adopted in many routine laboratories to reduce the presence of matrix interference with good results. An important advantage of this approach is its general applicability, although without considering specific co-extractives. Therefore, the use of highly sensitive instrumentation is essential to cover the pesticides analyzed by this approach. Gas and liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometry are currently the most widely used for monitoring pesticides in food, but high-resolution mass spectrometry is starting to be used more often as it provides greater selectivity and more extensive analysis. However, the lack of sensitivity compared to tandem quadrupole mass spectrometry requires higher amount of sample injected (e.g. 1 g) that increases the matrix effect greatly. Improvements in sensitivity are expected for these MS platforms, which will allow them to be more effectively

applied to highly complex matrices such as spices.

New chromatographic approaches, such as the use of supercritical fluid extraction coupled to ESI-MS that facilitates the decrease of matrix effects can be a good alternative in future developments. In all literature revised there is a lack of validated methodologies for analytes not well covered by classical multiresidue methods. Therefore, the development of methods for group of compounds with especial difficulties such as high polar herbicides should be considered for future studies.

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References

- [1] Codex Committee on Pesticide Residues of February 2018 on Revision of the Classification of Food and Feed. Group 028 Spices, <http://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius/resources/circular-letters/en> (accessed on March 2019).
- [2] FAO, Herbs, Spices and Essential Oils: Post-harvest Operations in Developing Countries, UNIDO and FAO, 2005. <http://www.fao.org/3/a-ad420e.pdf>. (Accessed December 2018).
- [3] T.K. Lim, Edible Medicinal and Non-medicinal Plants, vol.12, Modified Stems, Roots, Bulbs, Springer, Switzerland, 2016.
- [4] D.J. Charles, Antioxidant Properties of Spices, Herbs and Other Sources, Springer, New York), 2013.
- [5] C. Ferrer Amate, H. Unterluggauer, R.J. Fischer, A.R. Fernández-Alba, S. Masselter, Development and validation of a LC-MS/MS method for the simultaneous determination of aflatoxins, dyes and pesticides in spices, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 397 (2010) 93-107.
- [6] S. Uclés, A. Lozano, A. Sosa, P. Parrilla Vázquez, A. Valverde, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Matrix interference evaluation employing GC and LC coupled to triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometry, *Talanta* 174 (2017) 72-81.
- [7] U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. <https://www.epa.gov/pesticide-tolerances> (accessed March 2019).
- [8] Codex Alimentarius, International Food Standards. <https://www.fao.org/fao-who-codexalimentarius>. (Accessed December 2018).
- [9] Regulation (EC) N° 396/2005 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 February 2005 on Maximum Residue Levels of Pesticides in or on Food and Feed of Plant and Animal Origin and Amending Council Directive 91/414/EEC, http://ec.europa.eu/sanco_pesticides/public/index.cfm (accessed on March 2019).
- [10] Regulation 149/2008, Maximum Pesticide Levels for Food Products for Human Consumption and Animal Feedingstuffs, L58, European Union, Off. J. Eur. Union, 2008. (1 March 2008).
- [11] ESA Dehydration Factors, Working Document, June 2003. <http://www.esa-spices.org/documents>. (Accessed March 2019).
- [12] The 2015 European Union Report on pesticide residues in food, *EFSA J* 15 (4)

(2017) 4791. <http://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2017.4791>.

- [13] The 2016 European Union Report on pesticide residues in food, *EFSA J* 16 (7) (2018) 5348. <http://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5348>.
- [14] K.S.Y. Leung, K. Chan, C.L. Chan, G.H. Lu, Systematic evaluation of organochlorine pesticide residues in Chinese materia medica, *Phytother Res.* 19 (6) (2005) 514-518.
- [15] N. Sun, L. Hao, J. Xue, H. Jin, J. Tian, R. Lin, Multi-residue analysis of 18 organochlorine pesticides in 10 traditional Chinese medicines by gas chromatography (GC), *J. Health Sci.* 53 (4) (2007) 464-469.
- [16] J. Xue, L. Hao, F. Peng, Residues of 18 organochlorine pesticides in 30 traditional Chinese medicines, *Chemosphere* 71 (2008) 1051-1055.
- [17] M.V.N. Rodrigues, F.G.R. Reyes, P.M. Magalhaesa, S. Rath, GC-MS determination of organochlorine pesticides in medicinal plants harvested in Brazil, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.* 18 (1) (2007) 135-142.
- [18] A.A.K. Abou-Arab, M.S. Kawther, M.E.E. Tantawy, I.R. Badea, N. Khayria, Quantify estimation of some contaminants in commonly used medicinal plants in the Egyptian market, *Food Chem.* 67 (1999) 357-363.
- [19] E.D. van Asselt, J.L. Banach, H.J. van der Fels-Klerx, Prioritization of chemical hazards in spices and herbs for European monitoring programs, *Food Control* 83 (2018) 7-17.
- [20] WHO, GEMS/Food Contamination Database. <https://extranet.who.int/gemsfood/>. (accessed on March 2019).
- [21] L. Maggi, M. Carmona, C.P. del Campo, A. Zalacain, J.H. de Mendoza, F.A. Mocholí, G.L. Alonso, Multi-residue contaminants and pollutants analysis in saffron spice by stir bar sorptive extraction and gas chromatography-ion trap tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1209 (2008) 55-60.
- [22] O. Lacina, M. Zachariasova, J. Urbanova, M. Vaclavikova, T. Cajka, J. Hajslova, Critical assessment of extraction methods for the simultaneous determination of pesticide residues and mycotoxins in fruits, cereals, spices and oil seeds employing ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1262 (2012) 8-18.
- [23] B. Lozowicka, M. Jankowska, E. Rutkowska, I. Hrynko, P. Kaczynski, J. Micinski, The evaluation of a fast and simple pesticide multiresidue method in various herbs by gas chromatography, *J. Nat. Med.* 68 (2014) 95-111.
- [24] J. Xue, Y. Xu, F. Liu, J. Xue, H. Li, W. Peng, Comparison of different sample pre-

treatments for multi-residue analysis of organochlorine and pyrethroid pesticides in chrysanthemum by gas chromatography with electron capture detection, *J. Sep. Sci.* 36 (2013) 1311-1316.

- [25] D.G. Hayward, J.W. Wong, Organohalogen and organophosphorous pesticide method for ginseng root e a comparison of gas chromatography-single quadrupole mass spectrometry with high resolution time-of-flight mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 81 (2009) 5716-5723.
- [26] L.-K. Chai, F. Elie, A rapid multi-residue method for pesticide residues determination in white and black pepper (*Piper nigrum* L.), *Food Control* 32 (2013) 322-326.
- [27] H. Tong, Y. Tong, J. Xue, D. Liu, X. Wu, Multi-residual pesticide monitoring in commercial Chinese herbal medicines by gas chromatography-triple quadrupole tandem mass spectrometry, *Food Anal. Methods* 7 (2014) 135-145.
- [28] A. Goon, Z. Khan, D. Oulkar, R. Shinde, S. Gaikwad, K. Banerjee, A simultaneous screening and quantitative method for the multiresidue analysis of pesticides in spices using ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-high resolution (Orbitrap) mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1532 (2018) 105-111.
- [29] S.C. Moldoveanu, V. Daniel, *Sample Preparation in Chromatography*, Elsevier Science, Amsterdam, 2002, pp. 394-396.
- [30] Z. Machalova, M. Sajfrtova, R. Pavela, M. Topiar, Extraction of botanical pesticides from *Pelargonium graveolens* using supercritical carbon dioxide, *Ind. Crops Prod.* 67 (2015) 310-317.
- [31] G. Du, Y. Xiao, H.R. Yang, L. Wang, Y.I. Song, Y.T. Wang, Rapid determination of pesticide residues in herbs using selective pressurized liquid extraction and fast gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry, *J. Sep. Sci.* 35 (2012) 1922-1932.
- [32] M. Rezaee, Y. Assadi, M.R. Milani Hosseini, E. Aghaee, F. Ahmadi, S. Berijani, Determination of organic compounds in water using dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1116 (2006) 1-9.
- [33] B.S. Inbaraj, H. Lu, T.H. Kao, B.H. Chen, Simultaneous determination of phenolic acids and flavonoids in *Lycium barbarum* Linnaeus by HPLC-DAD-ESI-MS, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 51 (2010) 549-556.
- [34] H. Yee-Man, T. Yeuk-Ki, L.K. Sze-Yin, Highly sensitive and selective organophosphate screening in twelve commodities of fruits, vegetables and herbal medicines by dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction, *Anal. Chim. Acta* 775 (2013) 58-66.

- [35] M. Anastassiades, S.J. Lehotay, D. Stajnbaher, F.J. Schenck, Fast and easy multiresidue method employing acetonitrile extraction/partitioning and “dispersive solid-phase extraction” for the determination of pesticide residues in produce, *J. AOAC Int.* 86 (2003) 412-431.
- [36] M.Á. González-Curbelo, B. Socas-Rodríguez, A.V. Herrera-Herrera, J. González-Sálamo, J. Hernández-Borges, M.Á. Rodríguez-Delgado, Evolution and applications of the QuEChERS method, *TrAC Trends Anal. Chem. (Reference Ed.)* 71 (2015) 169-185.
- [37] EN 15662: 2008, Foods of Plant Origin-Determination of Pesticide Residues Using GC-MS And/or LC-MS/MS Following Acetonitrile Extraction and Partitioning and Clean-Up by Dispersive SPE, QuEChERS method, Brussels, Belgium, 2008.
- [38] AOAC Official Method 2007.01, Pesticide Residues in Foods by Acetonitrile Extraction and Partitioning with Magnesium Sulfate, AOAC Int., Gaithersburg, USA, 2007.
- [39] T.P.A. Shabeer, R. Girame, S. Utture, D. Oulkar, K. Banerjee, D. Ajay, R. Arimboor, K.R.K. Menon, Optimization of multiresidue method for targeted screening and quantitation of 243 pesticide residues in cardamom (*Elettaria cardamomum*) by gas chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (GC-MS/MS) analysis, *Chemosphere* 193 (2018) 447-453.
- [40] I. Reinholds, I. Pugajeva, V. Bartkevics, A reliable screening of mycotoxins and pesticide residues in paprika using ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to high resolution Orbitrap mass spectrometry, *Food Control* 60 (2016) 683-689.
- [41] S. Chawla, H.K. Patel, H.N. Gor, K.M. Vaghela, P.P. Solanki, P.G. Shah, Evaluation of matrix effects in multiresidue analysis of pesticide residues in vegetables and spices by LC-MS/MS, *J. AOAC Int.* 100 (3) (2017) 616-623.
- [42] M. Anastassiades, E. Scherbaum, B. Tsdelen, D. Stajnbaher, Recent developments in QuEChERS methodology for pesticide multiresidue analysis, in: H. Ohkawa, H. Miyagawa, P.W. Lee (Editors), *Pesticide Chemistry. Crop Protection, Public Health, Environmental Safety*, Wiley-VCH Verlag GmbH & Co. KGaA, Weinheim, 2007.
- [43] E. Rutkowska, B. Lozowicka, P. Kaczynski, Modification of multiresidue QuEChERS protocol to minimize matrix effect and improve recoveries for determination of pesticide residues in dried herbs followed by GC-MS/MS, *Food*

Anal. Methods 11 (2018) 709-724.

- [44] M. Jadhav, A.Sh Thekkumpurath, M. Nakade, M. Gadgil, D. Oulkar, R. Arimboor, M. Ramkrishna, K. Banerjee, Multiresidue method for targeted screening of pesticide residues in spice cardamom (*Elettaria cardamomum*) by Liquid Chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry, *J. AOAC Int.* 100 (3) (2017) 603-609.
- [45] L. Rajska, A. Lozano, A. Uclés, C. Ferrer, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Determination of pesticide residues in high oil vegetal commodities by using various multi-residue methods and clean-ups followed by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1304 (2013) 109-120.
- [46] T. Tuzimski, T. Rejczak, Application of HPLC-DAD after SPE/QuEChERS with ZrO₂-based sorbent in d-SPE clean-up step for pesticide analysis in edible oils, *Food Chem.* 190 (2016) 71-79.
- [47] P. Parrilla Vázquez, E. Hakme, S. Uclés, V. Cutillas, M. Martínez Galera, A.R. Mughari, A.R. Fernández-Alba, Large multiresidue analysis of pesticides in edible vegetable oils by using efficient solid-phase extraction sorbents based on quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged and safe methodology followed by gas chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1463 (2016) 20-31.
- [48] R. López-Blanco, R. Nortes-Méndez, J. Robles-Molina, D. Moreno-González, B. Gilbert-López, J.F. García-Reyes, A. Molina-Díaz, Evaluation of different cleanup sorbents for multiresidue pesticide analysis in fatty vegetable matrices by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1456 (2016) 89-104.
- [49] M. Urban, C. Lesueur, Comparing d-SPE sorbents of the QuEChERS extraction method and EMR-Lipid for the determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in food of animal and plant origin, *Food Anal. Methods* 10 (2017) 2111-2124.
- [50] E. Hakme, A. Lozano, S. Uclés, M.M. Gómez-Ramos, A.R. Fernández-Alba, High-throughput gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis of pesticide residues in spices by using the enhanced matrix removal-lipid and the sample dilution approach, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1573 (2018) 28-41.
- [51] S.J. Lehotay, K.A. Son, H. Kwon, U. Koesukwiwat, W. Fu, K. Mastovska, E. Hoh,

- N. Leepipatpiboon, Comparison of QuEChERS sample preparation methods for the analysis of pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1217 (2010) 2548-2560.
- [52] M.M. Rao, A.K. Galib, Detection of toxic heavy metals and pesticide residue in herbal plants which are commonly used in the herbal formulations, *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 181 (2011) 267-271.
- [53] W. Yi-Qun, M. Xue-Jin, Y. Ai-Ping, Sh Ming-Yue, W. Yu-Mei, Simultaneous determination of organophosphorus pesticides in Chinese herbal medicines by microwave-assisted extraction coupled with dispersive-solid phase extraction and gas chromatography, *Biomed. Chromatogr.* 24 (2010) 961-968.
- [54] T. Tuzimski, Determination of analytes in medical herbs extracts by SPE coupled with two-dimensional planar chromatography in combination with diode array scanning densitometry and HPLC-diode array detector, *J. Sep. Sci.* 34 (2011) 27-36.
- [55] V. Tripathy, A. Saha, J. Kumar, Detection of pesticides in popular medicinal herbs : a modified, QuEChERS and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry based approach, *J. Food Sci. Technol.* 54 (2) (2017) 458-468.
- [56] P.H. Viana de Carvalho, A.S. Barreto, M.O. Rodrigues, V.M. Prata, P.B. Alves, M.E. de Mesquita, S.A. Júnior, S. Navickiene, Two-dimensional coordination polymer matrix for solid-phase extraction of pesticide residues from plant *Cordia salicifolia*, *J. Sep. Sci.* 32 (2009) 2132-2138.
- [57] H. Bao-Huey, L. Maw-Rong, Solid-phase microextraction for organochlorine pesticide residues analysis in Chinese herbal formulations, *J. Chromatogr. A* 898 (2000) 245-256.
- [58] Y. Wang, H.-Y. Jin, Sh-Ch Ma, J. Lu, R.-Ch Lin, Determination of 195 pesticide residues in Chinese herbs by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry using analyte protectants, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1218 (2011) 334-342.
- [59] A. Sadowska-Rociek, M. Surma, E. Cieslik, Application of QuEChERS method for simultaneous determination of pesticide residues and PAHs in fresh herbs, *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 90 (2013) 508-513.
- [60] M.M. Storelli, Evaluation of toxic metal (Hg, Cd, Pb), polychlorinated biphenyl (PCBs), and pesticide (DDTs) levels in aromatic herbs collected in selected areas of Southern Italy, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 21 (2014) 946-953.
- [61] T.D. Nguyen, K.J. Lee, M.H. Lee, G.H. Lee, A multiresidue method for the determination 234 pesticides in Korean herbs using gas chromatography

mass spectrometry, *Microchem. J.* 95 (2010) 43-49.

- [62] European Commission, Document No. SANTE/11945/2016, Guidance Document on Analytical Quality Control and Method Validation Procedures for Pesticide Residues Analysis in Food and Feed, European Commission, 2015.
- [63] X-q. Liu, Y-f. Li, W-t. Meng, D-x. Li, H. Sun, L. Tong, G-x. Sun, A multi-residue method for simultaneous determination of 74 pesticides in Chinese material medica using modified QuEChERS sample preparation procedure and gas chromatography tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. B* 1015-1016 (2016) 1-12.
- [64] X. Duan, L. Tong, D. Li, Zh Yu, Y. Zhao, A multiresidue method for simultaneous determination of 116 pesticides in *Notoginseng Radix et Rhizoma* using modified QuEChERS coupled with gas chromatography tandem mass spectrometry and census 180 batches of sample from Yunnan province, *Chromatographia* 81 (2018) 545-556.
- [65] S. Kittlaus, J. Schimanke, G. Kempe, K. Speer, Development and validation of an efficient automated method for the analysis of 300 pesticides in foods using two-dimensional liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1283 (2013) 98-109.
- [66] F. Gosetti, E. Muzzucco, D. Zampieri, M.C. Gennaro, Signal suppression/enhancement in high-performance liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1217 (2010) 3929-3937.
- [67] M. Došmálková, E. Matisová, Fast gas chromatography for pesticide residues analysis, *J. Chromatogr. A* 1207 (2008) 1-16.
- [68] H. Stahnke, L. Alder, Matrix effects in liquid chromatography-electrospray ionization-mass spectrometry, in: D. Tsipi, H. Botitsi, A. Economou (Editors), *Mass Spectrometry for the Analysis of Pesticide Residues and Their Metabolites*, Wiley, NJ, USA, 2015 (ISBN: 978-1-118-50017-0).
- [69] P.N. Shaw, S.K. Tan, A. Hewavitharana, Strategies for the detection and elimination of matrix effects in quantitative LC-MS analysis, *LC GC Int.* 32 (1) (2014) 54-64.
- [70] P. Kaczynski, Clean-up and matrix effect in LC-MS/MS analysis of food of plant origin for high polar herbicides, *Food Chem.* 230 (2017) 524-531.
- [71] E. Akono Nantia, D. Moreno-González, F.P.T. Manfo, L. Gámiz-Gracia,

A.M. García-Campaña, QuEChERS-based method for the determination of carbamate residues in aromatic herbs by UHPLC-MS/MS, *Food Chem.* 216 (2017) 334-341.

[72] S.M. Taha, S.A. Gadalla, Development of an efficient method for multi residue analysis of 160 pesticides in herbal plant by ethyl acetate hexane mixture with direct injection to GC-MS/MS, *Talanta* 174 (2017) 767-779.

Fig. 1. Matrix effect for different spice matrices in LC-MS/MS. Liquid-solid extraction with acetonitrile followed by ultrasonication (30 min) without any further clean-up step being used for sample extraction. Printed with the permission of [11].

Table 1. MRL exceedances for peppercorn (black, green and white) from National report on pesticide residue analysis performed in 2016 (The 2016 European Union report on pesticide residues in food. Supplement MRL 2016 exceedances, EFSA 2018).

Pesticide	Result value (mg/kg)	MRL (mg/kg)
Carbendazim	0.56	0.10
Carbendazim	2.60	0.10
Imidacloprid	0.24	0.05
Carbendazim	0.17 ^a	0.10
Carbendazim	0.12 ^a	0.10
Carbendazim	0.18 ^a	0.10
Carbendazim	0.27	0.10
Carbendazim	0.27	0.10
Metalaxyl	0.15 ^a	0.10
Propamocarb	0.13	0.05
Carbendazim	0.28	0.10
Anthraquinone	0.02 ^a	0.02
Metalaxyl	0.15 ^a	0.10

^a Only numerical exceedance; compliant considering 50% expanded measurement uncertainty.

Table 2. Summary of extraction and analytical procedures used for the determination of pesticide residues in spices and herbs as a food over a 10th year period (2008-2018), including recoveries, RSDs, and LOQs.

	Analytes	Matrix	Extraction method	Analytical instrument	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Year	Ref.
LSE	163 pesticides	6 herbs (chamomile, linden, lungwort, melissa, peppermint and thyme) (2 g)	50 mL hexane/diethyl ether/acetone (1:2:2, v/v/v) for 30 min, then 20 mL hexane/diethyl ether/acetone (1:2:2, v/v/v) for 30 min followed by clean-up using a column of 2 g sodium sulfate, 5% neutral aluminium oxide (2.5 g) and 4% Florisil (2 g). Elution with 30 mL hexane/dichloromethane (7:3, v/v)	GC-ECD GC-NPD	70-118	<18	-	2014	[23]
	21 pesticides	7 culinary spices (1 g)	Vortex with 10 mL acetonitrile followed by ultrasonic bath for 30 min	LC-MS/MS	60-140	<16	0.2-43	2010	[5]
GPC	170 pesticides	Spices (ginseng) (2.5 g)	Extraction 2 times with 25 mL EtOAc followed by GPC and SPE cartridge (GCB, PSA)	GC-MS GC-HR-TOFMS	75-93	3-8	3-4	2009	[25]
SPE	16 pesticides	Spices (white and black pepper) (2 g)	Extraction with 20 mL AcN containing 1% acetic acid, MgSO_4 . SPE Pasteur glass pipette containing 0.5 g silica gel and eluted with 2 mL n-hexane:dichloromethane (4:1, v/v) and 2 mL n-hexane:dichloromethane (1:1, v/v)	GC-ECD	87-118	<11	20-100	2013	[26]
	199 pesticides	Spices (black pepper, cardamom, chili, coriander, cumin and turmeric) (2 g)	10 mL water + 10 mL AcN, QuEChERS (4 g MgSO_4 + 1 g NaCl), SPE with HLB cartridge, eluted with 1 mL AcN	UHPLC-Orbitrap-MS	70-120	<20	10-20	2018	[28]
MSPD	163 pesticides	6 herbs (chamomile, linden, lungwort, Melissa, peppermint and thyme) (2 g)	Ground herb blended with 4 g Florisil followed by clean-up using a column of 5 g sodium sulfate, 1 g C_{18} and 2.5 g silica gel. Elution with 25 mL acetone/methanol (9:1, v/v)	GC-ECD GC-NPD	70-119	≤ 16	5-40	2014	[23]
PLE	52 pesticides	Medicine and food dual-purpose herbs (5 g)	PLE with ethyl acetate, 120°C, 6 min, 50% of flush volume extracted for two cycles. 5 g	GC-MS/MS	81-118	3-12	1000-10000	2012	[31]
SBSE	46 pesticides	Spices (saffron) (1 g)	Florisil + 0.1 g GCB as SPLE sorbents SBSE (100 mL sample solution, 1 g/L, 1 mL MeOH, 20 g Na_2SO_4 . PDMS stir bars, stirring at 1000 rpm at room temperature for 14 h. Thermal desorption	GC-MS	75-111	6-22	0.13-4	2008	[21]

DLLME 10 organophosphorus pesticides
Dried herbs (0.1 g) DLLME with AcN and CCl₄ (50°C) GC-MS 70-119 3-10 1×10^{-4} - 5×10^{-3} 2013 [\[34\]](#)

Table 3. Summary of applications of the QuEChERS method to the analysis of pesticides in spices and herbs.

d-SPE clean-up	Analytes	Sample	R (%)	RSD (%)	Instrumentation	ME (%)	LOQ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Ref.
PSA/Florisil	160 pesticides	Herbs (chamomile, thyme, marjoram)	60-140	<20	GC-MS/MS	>100	10-250	[72]
C ₁₈ /MgSO ₄	28 carbamates	Aromatic herbs	72-97	<15	UHPLC-MS/MS	(-20)-(-70)	2	[71]
PSA/ENVI-Carb/MgSO ₄	235 pesticides	Dried herbs	60-130	<18	GC-MS/MS	(-59)-(69)	1-2	[43]
PSA/C ₁₈ /MgSO ₄	38 pesticides	Spices (capsicum, cumin, brinjal)	70-130	-	LC-MS/MS	(-5)-(661)	50	[41]
C ₁₈ /MgSO ₄	23 pesticides	Spices (paprika and black pepper)	70-120	<20	UHPLC-MS/MS	(-30)-(-70) Diluted extracts	11-50	[22]
PSA/MgSO ₄	154 pesticides	Spices (cardamom)	70-120	<20	LC-MS/MS	(-20)-(-98)	1-10	[44]
PSA/C ₁₈ /GCB/MgSO ₄	243 pesticides	Aromatic herbs (cardamom)	70-120	\leq 20	GC-MS/MS	e	10-50	[39]
HLB (SPE cartridge)	199 pesticides	Spices (black pepper, cardamom, chili, coriander, cumin, turmeric)	60-140	<20	UHPLC-Orbitrap-MS	(-20)-(-50)	10-20	[28]
EMR-Lipid	205 pesticides	Spices (black pepper, cayenne)	70-120	<20	GC-MS/MS	(-20)-(-50)	50	[50]

Table 4. Applications and limitations of the main d-SPE sorbents used in QuEChERS method.

Sorbent	Applications	Limitations/interactions with analytes	Ref.
PSA (Primary secondary amine)	To remove various polar organic acids, polar pigments, some sugars and fatty acids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some pH-sensitive pesticides (base-labile compounds) can suffer hydrolyzation under basic conditions in the d-SPE resulting in pH values which may exceed 8. To reduce pH is necessary to use formic acid after PSA clean-up Further clean-up is still desirable for samples which contain high amounts of lipids 	[44,55]
Florisil (Magnesium silicate)	Removes polar and low-fat co-extracts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low recoveries for high polar pesticides (trimethylsulfonium, chlormequat, mepiquat, paraquat, diquat) Further clean-up is still desirable 	[70]
C18 (Octadecyl)	Non-polar interfering substances could be removed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recoveries of the more lipophilic pesticides may suffer (a-HCH, b-HCH, lindane, p,p'-DDE, p,p'-DDD, o,p'-DDT, p,p'-DDT, benthio carb, benfuracarb, furathiocarb) Further clean-up is still desirable 	[43,71]
GCB (graphitized carbon black)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used to remove sterols, pigments such as chlorophyll and components of spice essential oils such as isopulegol acetate, carveol and caryophyllene oxide 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GCB retains apolar pesticides, especially those with planar ring structures (cyprodinil, fenazaquin, mepanipyrim, Pyrimethanil, prochloraz, quinoxifen, emamectin benzoate, spinosyn A, spinosyn D, spinetoram, carbendazim, thiabendazole, chlorothalonil, propoxur, hexachlorobenzene, aldrin, permethrin I and II, chlorpyrifos) 	[28,39,43]
Z-Sep, Z-Sep ⁺ (Zirconia-based sorbents)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For removal of lipids from fatty samples Enhance matrix clean-up compared to PSA, C18 and GCB sorbents 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further clean-up is still desirable Adsorption of compounds containing atoms donors of electrons that could interact with the ZrO₂ sorbent. This fact explains analyte loss for hydroxyl (cyproconazole, diclobutrazole, tebuconazole, metconazole, flutriafol and fenarimol), carboxylic acid-containing (fluzifop), hydroxyacetate (chlorobenzilate, bromopropylate) and phosphate (paraoxon-methyl, dichlorvos) compounds For pesticides having planar structures with chloride atoms, such as chlorothalonil, a very low recovery is also obtained 	[43]
ChloroFiltr (polymeric sorbent)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Removes chlorophyll 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further clean-up is still desirable Scarcely explored for pesticides in herbs 	[43]
ENVI-Carb (graphitized carbon sorbent)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Used to remove pigments, polyphenols and other polar compounds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further clean-up is still desirable Scarcely explored for pesticides in spices and herbs 	[43]
EMR-Lipid (Size exclusion and hydrophobic interaction)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For highly selective lipid removal Provides more robust and effective sample preparation for multiresidue analysis of pesticides in fatty matrices by GC-MS/MS and LC-MS/MS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scarcely explored for pesticides in spices and herbs 	

